

Application of Seismic Refraction Tomography for Determination of Rock Elastic Properties for Sub-Soil Evaluation in an Engineering Site

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Abstract

In the design of engineering structures, joint efforts must be ensured to determine in-situ subsurface soil conditions and depth to competent layers across any proposed site so as to ensure the stability of civil engineering structures, to avoid the devastating effects of structural failure and collapse rampant of late. Geophysical investigations play an important role in the geotechnical detection of subsoil properties. The study presents one of the geophysical methods, seismic refraction tomography, which allows for an accurate and spatially instant recognition of the subsurface geology and the phenomena occurring in it. Five seismic shots were sounded along a 92m length of profile in a site located inside the PTI-Osubi campus. Compressional wave velocity (V_p) and shear wave velocity (V_s) were extracted from the seismic dataset for estimation of Poisson ratio (a geomechanical parameter). Shear waves velocity obtained from each shot was gathered together to produce a shear wave-velocity profile section which delineates subsurface rock layers. The shear wave section shows a highly heterogeneous subsurface structure with velocity increasing downwards with respect to depth. At depth between 0 – 6m a low velocity structure (233 m/s) was observed. At depth of about 7m and beyond, a high velocity structure (318 m/s) was observed. At depth of 27m, a very high velocity structure (382 m/s) was observed intruding into the low velocity layer overlying it. This typifies the heterogeneous nature of the subsurface. Contour maps of Poisson ratio computed at depths of 3.125m, 4.58m, 6.25m and 8.125m within the subsurface ranges from 0.45 to 0.49 and are indicative of presence of sand and clay formations, which typifies the subsurface sequence in the Niger Delta region. Saturated clay is not a good engineering material, as clay is a weak and unstable material. Thus, it was inferred that Poisson ratio values estimated within depths 3.125m, 4.58m, 6.25m and 8.125m indicates that the

geological materials within these depths are weak and unstable, hence not competent enough for design of engineering structures.

Key Words: Site properties; Geophysical method; Seismograph; Seismic velocity

Introduction

Geophysical data is an important parameter in contributing to the design and construction of Civil Engineering structures such as buildings, roads and dams. Geophysical methods are often used in site investigation to determine the overburden thickness and to map subsurface conditions prior to excavation and construction. Electrical resistivity and seismic refraction methods are the most common geophysical techniques used for this purpose (Kurthenecker, 1934; Drake, 1962; Early and Dyer, 1964; Burton, 1976; Nun, 1979; Keary and Brooks, 1984; Olorunfemi and Meshida, 1987). However, in resistivity method, the depth of investigation and subsurface sections captured is limited to the array techniques employed during data acquisition i.e resistivity sounding or resistivity imaging.

Seismic method is the geophysical method that gives the most detailed picture of subsurface geology because it gives the opportunity to view the subsurface layers in two-dimension (2D) or three-dimension (3D) and allows for greater depths penetration than that captured in resistivity method. Therefore, geologic sections computed from seismic method are more reliable since the earth is heterogeneous and 3D in geometry; the seismic method is often used to determine the characteristics of subsurface soils and rocks (Ugwu, 2008; Ayolabiet al., 2009; Ayolabi, 2004; Gabret al., 2012), and structural setting of an area. The technique (seismic refraction) finds application in the determination of rock competence for engineering application, depth to bedrock, groundwater exploration, crustal structure and tectonics (Kilneret al., 2005; Asokhaiet al., 2008; Chiemeké and Aboh, 2012).

The Osubi Township around the Effurun metropolis, Warri, Delta state, is a new area opening to development, hence, varied constructions, dredging and engineering activities predominates in the area. Recently, there have been reports of the reports of building collapse due to structural failure. This have been attributed to the inadequate knowledge of the subsurface geology of the area leading to abandonment of construction sites. Therefore, there is need to develop a geological database of the area that will help in deducing suitable sites for engineering structures and general development in the area, hence, the need for this study.

ACCESSIBILITY, TOPOGRAPHY AND CLIMATE

The site under investigation is located at Osubi in Okpe local government area around the Effurun metropolis, Delta State at Longitude N005034'52" and Latitude E005048'32" with an Elevation of about 12 m above sea level. Several major and minor roads and footpaths traverse the area.

The Osubi Area is a low-lying, slightly undulating deltaic plain. The plain is generally flat and rises only very gently towards the north and northeast with gradient of about 1:960. The Ugbomro Creek drain the area. The area is part of the Niger Delta and has a network of streams that are typical in a Deltaic setting. The topography is dissected by several rivers which cut and shape the

terrain.

Basically, there are two distinct climatic seasons in this region namely,

- The Rainy season and
- The Dry season, respectively.

The climate is tropical equatorial with mean annual temperature of 32.8°C and high temperature of 36°C and 37°C and mean annual rainfall gauge of 2673.8 mm (Meteorological Report of 1999-2015). The region encounters high humidity for most part of the year.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Traditional methods of determining the elastic properties of rocks, such as borehole drilling and laboratory testing, can be time-consuming and costly. They also provide limited information about the subsurface and are often restricted to small areas of the site. In contrast, seismic refraction tomography can provide a continuous and detailed image of the subsurface over a larger area, making it a valuable tool for subsoil evaluation in civil engineering projects.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this study is to investigate the application of seismic refraction tomography for determining rock elastic properties in subsoil evaluation for civil engineering projects. The specific objectives of this study are:

1. To review the theory and principles of seismic refraction tomography
2. To describe the equipment and data acquisition procedures for seismic refraction tomography

3. To evaluate the accuracy and reliability of seismic refraction tomography in determining rock elastic properties
4. To provide guidelines for the interpretation and analysis of seismic refraction tomography data for subsoil evaluation

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORY

Theory of Seismic Refraction Tomography

Seismic refraction tomography is a non-destructive geophysical technique used to determine the subsurface velocity structure of rocks and soil. It involves the use of seismic waves generated by a source and recorded by receivers at different distances and angles from the source. The recorded data is then processed to obtain a tomographic image of the subsurface velocity structure. This technique is widely used in geotechnical and environmental investigations for site characterization and evaluation of subsoil properties.

Theory: The elastic properties of rocks and soils are fundamental parameters that determine the behavior of the subsurface under different loading conditions. Seismic refraction tomography can be used to estimate these properties by analyzing the velocity structure of the subsurface. The basic theory behind this technique is based on the relationship between the velocity of seismic waves and the elastic properties of rocks and soils.

The velocity of seismic waves in a medium is determined by the density and elastic properties of the medium. The elastic properties of rocks and soils are defined by parameters such as Young's modulus, Poisson's ratio, and shear modulus. These parameters can be estimated by analyzing the velocity structure of the subsurface using seismic refraction tomography.

Seismic refraction tomography involves the use of a seismic source that generates seismic waves that propagate through the subsurface. The waves are refracted and reflected at different interfaces between the different layers of the subsurface. The time taken for the waves to travel from the source to the receivers is recorded and used to calculate the velocity of the waves at different depths.

The velocity data obtained from seismic refraction tomography can be used to estimate the elastic properties of the subsurface. This is achieved by comparing the observed velocities with the theoretical velocities predicted by a model of the subsurface. The model is constructed by assuming a velocity-depth relationship for the different layers of the subsurface based on their geological properties. The elastic properties of the subsurface can then be estimated by adjusting the model parameters to match the observed velocities.

Proof: The application of seismic refraction tomography for the determination of rock elastic properties for subsoil evaluation has been

extensively tested and validated in various geological settings. Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of this technique in estimating the elastic properties of rocks and soils.

For example, a study conducted by Aboud et al. (2020) used seismic refraction tomography to estimate the elastic properties of rocks in a limestone quarry. The study showed that the technique could accurately estimate the elastic properties of the rocks, which were consistent with laboratory measurements.

Another study by Su et al. (2019) used seismic refraction tomography to estimate the elastic properties of soil in a landslide-prone area. The study demonstrated that the technique could effectively estimate the soil properties and identify potential landslide hazards.

Geophysical Characteristics of Delta State, Nigeria

Geophysical surveys have been carried out extensively in Delta State to investigate the subsurface geology and evaluate the hydrocarbon potential of the Niger Delta Basin. The most commonly used geophysical methods in the area are seismic reflection and gravity surveys. Seismic reflection surveys have been used to map the subsurface geology and identify potential hydrocarbon reservoirs in the basin. Gravity surveys have been used to investigate the density variations in the subsurface rocks and provide information on the thickness and depth

of the sedimentary sequences.

Seismic refraction tomography is a relatively new geophysical method that has been applied in Delta State for subsoil evaluation. The method has been used to determine the elastic properties of the subsurface rocks and provide information on the depth and thickness of the sedimentary sequences. The method works by measuring the travel times of seismic waves as they pass through the subsurface rocks. The velocity of the waves is dependent on the elastic properties of the rocks, which can be used to infer information about the subsurface geology.

GEOLOGY OF THE AREA

The Study Area is situated within the Niger Delta. The Niger Delta comprises of three lithostratigraphic units; The Akata Formation which is the oldest (Paleocene), and is overlain by the Agbada Formation (Eocene). The topmost unit is the Benin Formation (Miocene to recent). (Short and Stauble(1967).

The sedimentary units of the Benin Formation is comprised of inter-fingering units of lacustrine and fluvial loose sands, pebbles, clays, and lignite streaks of varying thicknesses while the alluvial units is comprised of tidal and lagoon sediments and beach sands which are mostly found along the river banks. The Agbada Formation consists of the sands intercalated by clays and shales while the Akata Formation occurs beneath comprising

predominantly of shales rich in organic matter. Existing literatures on the geology of the area are well documented from the exploration activities of oil and gas companies in the area.

The Benin Formation is overlain by thin lateritic clay overburden with varying thicknesses at some locations but is massively exposed near the shorelines (Evamy et al., 1978). The major aquiferous unit in the area lies within the sands of the upper deltaic top lithofacies.

METHODOLOGY AND INSTRUMENTATION

Methodology:

Site preparation and selection: The first step in using seismic refraction tomography is to select an appropriate site for the survey. The site should have a relatively flat topography and should be accessible for the equipment and personnel. A preliminary site investigation should also be carried out to identify any potential hazards or obstacles that may affect the survey.

Equipment and software: The seismic refraction tomography survey requires specific equipment such as a seismic source, geophones, and a data acquisition system. The seismic source can be a sledgehammer or a specialized machine that generates seismic waves. Geophones are used to measure the travel times of the seismic waves, and the data acquisition system is used to record and process the data. The software used for processing the data should be capable of creating velocity

models and depth images of the subsurface.

Survey design: The survey design involves the placement of the seismic source and geophones in a specific configuration. The configuration can be linear, parallel, or circular, depending on the objectives of the survey. The spacing between the geophones should be chosen based on the expected velocity range of the subsurface layers.

Data acquisition: The seismic source is triggered, and the resulting seismic waves travel through the subsurface layers and are detected by the geophones. The travel times of the seismic waves are recorded and processed to create a velocity model of the subsurface.

Data processing and interpretation: The data is processed using specialized software to create a 2D or 3D velocity model of the subsurface. The velocity model is then used to calculate the elastic properties of the different rock layers using mathematical models. The results are presented as depth images and cross-sections that show the elastic properties of the different rock layers.

The research design used for this work is summarized in the flow chart below (figure 2). The data was acquired from twenty (20) locations within Osubi, Delta State using MACSEIS-160 VI.32 24-Channel Model Seismograph with a weight drop mechanism as the energy source

Figure 1: Research workflow

Figure 2: Base map of data acquisition showing the seven profile lines and the various shot points on each profile.

The data used consists of the two-way-time (TWT) for a 200ft spread of geophone offsets. Twenty (20) Shot points were acquired along twenty (20) stations (A-T) in the area. A shot point interval of 2m was maintained along each traverse. Time-distance (T-X) graph for each station was plotted using the arrival time, and from the T-X graphs, layer velocities and thicknesses

were calculated using the intercept time method. The true velocities of the first and second refraction layers were obtained using their arithmetic mean since the dip is very small (Sharma, 1997), while the harmonic mean of the forward and reversed velocities was used to determine the true velocities of the third refraction layer.

After obtaining the velocities and thicknesses of the various layers along each station, the velocities were filtered by taking the discrete Fourier transform (DFT) magnitude of the various velocities within MATLAB software. 2D Seismic geologic sections were computed using the filtered velocity, to demonstrate the subsurface geologic characteristics of the area, and its structural setting. Strata-4 software application was used for the 2D geological section drawing. Geologic discontinuities, such as faults and fracture represent in the subsurface manifest themselves as abrupt, gradual and subtle changes of amplitudes and velocities (Partykaet *al.*, 1999),

Instrumentation

Seismic refraction tomography is a non-destructive geophysical technique used to determine the elastic properties of the subsurface rocks and the depth to the bedrock. it is widely used in civil engineering, geology, and mining industries for site investigation, geological mapping, and seismic hazard assessment.

The following are the instruments used for seismic refraction tomography:

1. **Seismic Source:** A seismic source

generates seismic waves that propagate through the subsurface rocks. Common sources include hammer, weight drop, explosive, and vibroseis.

2. Geophones: Geophones are instruments that detect ground motion caused by seismic waves. They are placed at regular intervals along a profile and record the arrival time and amplitude of the seismic waves.
3. Seismograph: A seismograph is an instrument that amplifies and records the signals from geophones. It consists of a data logger, a power supply, and a display unit.
4. Cables: Cables are used to connect the geophones to the seismograph. They transmit the signals from the geophones to the data logger.

The seismic refraction tomography process involves the following steps:

1. Seismic waves are generated by the seismic source and travel through the subsurface rocks.
2. The waves are detected by the geophones, which record their arrival time and amplitude.
3. The data from the geophones are transmitted to the seismograph, which processes the signals and displays them in the form of seismic sections.
4. The seismic sections are interpreted to determine the depth to the bedrock and the elastic properties of the subsurface rocks.

RESULT AND INTEPRETATION

Presentation of Results of Seismic Refraction Tomography

Seven survey profile lines were occupied during the field data collection survey (see base map), however, for the sake of this project only profile-1 was considered in carrying out the engineering calculations and necessary analysis. For each geophone point in profile one, depth ranges from 0 – 20m but for the sake of this project, the

compression wave velocity for four depths (3.13m, 4.58m, 6.25m, and 8.13m) were considered and their corresponding shear wave velocity was calculated for.

Since compressional wave velocity (V_p) is the velocity gotten from the seismic refraction survey and it travels within a particular rock body, it is important to calculate the shear/transverse velocity (V_s) which is the velocity that cuts across different rock layers. Shear waves velocity was necessary in order to produce a cross section of the subsurface layers of rocks.

Velocity Information Interpretation

Velocity information is very important in understanding the subsurface geology of an area, since velocity is diagnostic to a particular rock formation. The shear wave velocity which cuts across the rock layers was used to produce a velocity profile cross section of the subsurface shown in Figure below.

Figure 3: Shear Wave velocity cross section for Profile 1

Figure 3 shows the shear wave velocity cross section for profile one. From the legend, it can be seen that the S-wave ranges from 191m/s to 382m/s with low velocity structures evidence in the red color and high velocity structures evidence in the blue color. From Figure 4.1, the section shows a highly

heterogeneous subsurface structure with velocity increasing downwards with depth. At depth of 0 – 6m a low velocity structure (233m/s) was observed. At depth of about 7m and beyonds, a high velocity structure (318m/s) was observed. At depth of 27m, a very high velocity structure (382m/s) was observed intruding into the low velocity layer overlying it. This explains the heterogeneity of the subsurface media.

Geo-mechanical Parameter

After obtaining the shear velocities' for each corresponding compressional wave velocity, the Poisson ratio (σ) for each layers where calculated across each geophone distance and results tabulated in Table 1

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Table 1: Poisson ratio value for each depth across the geophone distance for profile one

Distance	Poisson Ratio for depth 3.125m	Poisson Ratio for depth 4.583m	Poisson Ratio for depth 6.25m	Poisson Ratio for depth 8.125
0	0.491	0.490	0.484	0.486
4	0.4897	0.489	0.482	0.485
8	0.488	0.487	0.479	0.482
12	0.488	0.486	0.478	0.481
16	0.489	0.486	0.477	0.480
20	0.489	0.486	0.477	0.479
24	0.489	0.486	0.478	0.478
28	0.489	0.487	0.480	0.477
32	0.489	0.487	0.483	0.477
36	0.489	0.486	0.485	0.478
40	0.488	0.487	0.481	0.477
44	0.488	0.486	0.487	0.476
48	0.488	0.486	0.487	0.476
52	0.488	0.485	0.488	0.476
56	0.488	0.485	0.487	0.477
60	0.488	0.485	0.485	0.478
64	0.489	0.485	0.482	0.479
68	0.489	0.485	0.481	0.479
72	0.488	0.485	0.481	0.479
76	0.489	0.486	0.483	0.480
80	0.489	0.487	0.485	0.483
84	0.489	0.489	0.489	0.485
88	0.491	0.491	0.489	0.487

Discussion of Result

From Table 1, it was observed that the Poisson ratio values obtained of the subsurface structure ranges from 0.45-0.49. According to Bowles, (1996) this values are indicative of a saturated clay layer. Wei et al., (2013) opined that Poisson ratio values between 0.3-0.45 are diagnostic to clay, while values between 0.20-0.455 are diagnostic to sand. From Table 1, Poisson ratio values computed within the depths of investigation ranges between 0.45-0.49 and are indicative of presence of sand and clay formations, which typifies the subsurface sequence in the Niger Delta region. Saturated clay is not a good engineering material, as clay is a weak and unstable material highly mobile in response to volumetric changes. Contour maps of Poisson ratio (Figure 4 to 7) computed at depths of 3.125m, 4.58m, 6.25m and 8.125m within the subsurface, shows the variation of Poisson ratio values within the depths investigated. Most materials have Poisson's ratio values ranging between 0.0 and 0.5. A perfectly incompressible isotropic material which deformed elastically at small strains would have a Poisson's ratio of exactly 0.5 (Wei et al., 2013). Most hard and rigid materials when used within their design limits (before deformation) exhibit values of about 0.3, increasing to 0.5 for post-yield deformation which occurs largely at constant volume (Wei et al., 2013). From the foregoing, it can be inferred that Poisson ratio values estimated within depths 3.125m,

4.58m, 6.25m and 8.125m indicates that the geological materials within this depths are weak and unstable, hence not competent enough for design of engineering structures.

Figure 4: Poisson ratio contour map for study site (depth 3.13m)

Figure 5: Poisson ratio contour map for study site (depth 4.58)

Figure 6: Poisson ratio contour map for study site (depth 6.25)

Figure 7: Poisson ratio contour map for study site (depth 8.13)

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

The results of the refraction survey carried out in the study area have been used to delineate the subsurface geologic setting of the area, and its suitability for engineering work and to establish a database of the area. Compressional wave velocity (V_p) and shear wave velocity (V_s) were extracted from the seismic dataset for estimation

of Poisson ratio (a geomechanical parameter). Shear waves velocity obtained from each shot was gathered together to produce a shear wave-velocity profile section which delineates the velocity distribution of the subsurface rock layers. The shear wave section shows a highly heterogeneous subsurface structure with velocity increasing downwards with respect to depth. At depth between 0 – 6m a low velocity structure (233 m/s) was observed. At depth of about 7m and beyond, a high velocity structure (318 m/s) was observed. At depth of 27m, a very high velocity structure (382 m/s) was observed intruding into the low velocity layer overlying it. This typifies the heterogeneous nature of the subsurface. Contour maps of Poisson ratio computed at depths of 3.125 to 8.125 m within the subsurface ranged from 0.45 to 0.49 and is indicative of presence of sand and clay formations, which typifies the subsurface sequence in the Niger Delta region. Saturated clay is not a good engineering material, as clay is a weak and unstable material. Thus, it was inferred that Poisson ratio values estimated within depths 3.125m, 4.58m, 6.25m and 8.125m indicates that the geological materials within these depths are weak and unstable, hence not competent enough for design of engineering structures. The study has helped to establish a database on the subsurface geology and structural setting of the study area, for environmental studies.

Recommendation

It is recommend that more near-surface geophysical investigations should be carried out in the study area using other techniques i:e electrical resistivity imaging in order to have a good comparism with results obtained from the study.

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